

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}[°]

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

[°]LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The Duration Index of Hot Periods in the Italian Regions

Between 2011 and 2022 it grew on average by 64.07%

Istat calculates the duration index of hot periods. The variable is defined as the number of days in the year in which the maximum temperature is above the 90th percentile of the distribution in the reference climatological period (1981-2010), for at least six consecutive days. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2011 and 2022.

Ranking of the regions by index of duration of hot periods in 2022. Lazio is in first place by value of the index of duration of hot periods in 2022 with a value of 63, followed by Umbria with a value of 61 and from Liguria with a value of 51.5. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a value of 42, followed by Basilicata with a value of 41, and Valle d'Aosta with 40.5 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a value of 31, followed by Puglia with a value of 29 and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 27.

Ranking of the regions by index of duration of hot periods between 2011 and 2022. Sardinia is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the index of duration of hot periods between 2011 and 2022 with a value of 616.67% corresponding to a growth from an amount of 6 units up to a value of 43 units. Calabria follows with a variation equal to +385.71% corresponding to a variation from 7 units up to 34 units. Molise is in third place with a value equal to 181.25% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 16 units up to a value of 45 units. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a variation equal to +75.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 24 units up to a value of 42 units. Puglia follows with a value of 70.59% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 17 units up to a value of 29 units. Below is Campania with a percentage change equal to 66.67% corresponding to a change from an amount of 24 units up to 40 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a value of -22.86% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 35 units up to a value of 27 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a variation of -31.11% corresponding to a variation from 45 to 31. It should be considered that the value of Sicily is also very significant. In fact, in Sicily in 2011 the duration index of hot periods was equal to 0 and reached a value of 35 in 2022. Between 2011 and 2022 the value of the index of duration of hot periods grew on average for the Italian regions from an amount of 25.4 units up to a value of 41.7 units or equal to an amount of 64.07%.

Italian macro-regions. The value of the index of the duration of hot periods between 2011 and 2022 grew in all Italian macro-regions with the exception of the North-East. Specifically, the index of the duration of hot periods grew in the North with a value equal to 5.71%, in the North-West with a value equal to +26.47%, in the Center by an amount equal to 71.88 %, in the South for an amount equal to 216.67% and in the South for an amount equal to 123.53%. The North-East is the only Italian macro-region in which there was a reduction in the value of the duration of the heat index equal to -8.33%.

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Molise, Calabria, Sicily, Abruzzo, Basilicata, Puglia, Sardinia, Marche, Campania;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Piedmont, Emilia-Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Lazio, Tuscany, Umbria, Liguria.

Comparing the two analyzed clusters we can notice the following ordering based on the average value, i.e.: $C1 > C2$. We can see that the regions of Cluster 1 are essentially the southern regions. On the contrary, the regions of Cluster 2 are the regions of the Centre-North. Therefore, the duration index of the hot period increased more in the southern regions than in the northern regions. However, if we look at the time series development of the graph of cluster 1 and cluster 2 then it turns out that cluster 1 was not always dominant compared to cluster 2 in the period 2011-2022. Specifically, there was a period between 2013 and 2014 in which the value of cluster 2 was higher than cluster 1. And there were four periods in which the value of Cluster 2 was exactly equal to the value of Cluster 1 that is, between 2012 and 2013, between 2014 and 2015, in 2016 and between 2020 and 2021. Therefore, the trend of the two clusters highlights a trend of growth in the value of the duration index of the hot period also if the dominance structure of the two clusters is not always clear.

Conclusions. From the analysis conducted we can summarize the following propositions:

- the value of the index of the duration of the hot period between 2011 and 2022 increased in all Italian regions with the exception of Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Friuli Venezia Giulia;
- the index of the duration of the hot period between 2011 and 2022 grew in all macro-regions with the exception of the North-East;
- The value of the heat period duration index tends to be higher on average for the southern regions than for the northern regions.

However, if we consider the average value for the Italian regions we note that between 2011 and 2022 the duration index of the hot period increased by 64%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Regioni	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	35	8	6	13	35	13	33	18	16	15	9	40
Valle d'Aosta	36	19	6	12	39	12	24	20	16	28,5	8,5	40,5

Liguria	28	15,5	6	7	18	15	12,5	18	24	21	8	51,5
Lombardia	34	16	12	13	36	14	23	19	20	20	2	42,5
Trentino-Alto Adige	35	13	13	6	53,5	20,5	21	16	17	15	2	27
Veneto	41	24	15	12	37	17	15	22	22	19	0	40
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	45	23	15	13	40	25	14	38	31	21	0	31
Emilia-Romagna	32	20	13	12	29	12	28	18	13,5	14	7	34
Toscana	33	20	13	13	23	8	23	16	14	25	20	48
Umbria	31	28	12	13	28	9	33	11	20	18	23	61
Marche	24	13	6	6	20	15	15	11	6	8	18	42
Lazio	31	19,5	12	13	25	15	27	15,5	21	17,5	25	63
Abruzzo	17	20	12	7	19	23	15	12,5	3	6	32,5	46
Molise	16	14	19	15	21	17	14	11	6	7	29	45
Campania	24	20	20	6	21,5	14	20	6	18,5	13	30	40
Puglia	17	19	14	16	20	21	19	13	13	8	24	29
Basilicata	16	15	22	17	28	8	18	9	10	13,5	28,5	41
Calabria	7	13	8	14	14	13	12	6	9	6	36	34
Sicilia	0	7	7	15	7	10	11	6	10	6	24	35
Sardegna	6	0	17	25	12	8	26	13	6	13	20	43

Rank	Regione	2022
1	Lazio	63
2	Umbria	61
3	Liguria	51,5
4	Toscana	48
5	Abruzzo	46
6	Molise	45
7	Sardegna	43

8	Lombardia	42,5
9	Marche	42
10	Basilicata	41
11	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	40,5
12	Piemonte	40
13	Veneto	40
14	Campania	40
15	Sicilia	35
16	Emilia-Romagna	34
17	Calabria	34
18	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	31
19	Puglia	29
20	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	27

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	35	15	12	12	36	14	25	19	18	17	3	37
Nord-ovest	34	13	7	13	36	14	28,5	19	19	19	6	43
Nord-est	36	19,5	13	12	36	16	21	19	18	16	2	33
Centro	32	20	12	13	24	9	24	16	17	18	21	55
Mezzogiorno	12	13	12	15	16	14	18	10	10	8	26	38
Sud	17	19	14	14	21	16	18	9	11	8	31	38
Isole	0	6	11	19	8	10	17	12	6	6	21	38

